

FRANCE

FRANCE

IN METALLURGICAL PROCESS MODELING SYSTEM HIGH TEMPERATURE COPPER REFINING PROCESSES

Tolibayev Yerlan Amangeldiyevich

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

Jienbaev Atabay Nietbay o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

Dauletbayev Zamir Tangjarbay o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li

Student of Nukus Mining Institute:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686909>

Abstract: Based on the partial removal of impurities present in copper refining in industrial metal smelting and refining enterprises oxygen increases dramatically. The most interesting centralized process copper processing is carried out in one factory. This is because copper from the manufacturing plants it was possible to determine that it has a different chemical composition, but its quantity is small. Therefore, a different amount of oxygen is required for a constantly changing weight average composition of liquid metal used for oxidizing and slagging compounds and in all similar processes. The purpose of the work is the method of creation a mathematical model for solving the single-criteria and multi-criteria problem of high temperature copper processing has been established. Algorithms of the model based on passive experience presented with selected assumptions and constraints. Mathematical models developed using correlational regression analysis. Outcome variable in models depends on the concentration of oxygen in the solution. Defined by the objective function were taken as the main variables of the cleaning process. The results of mathematical modeling allow us to quickly calculate the oxygen concentration in the air for the oxidation of mixtures, the state of dissolution of substances of different chemical composition in terms of quantity was observed. The models are consistent with the general theory of anode melting and can be used. This we can monitor and estimate the process.

Key words: Copper purification, oxidation rate, mathematical modeling, linear regression, copper chemical reactions

Introduction

Recently, a rapidly changing trend has been observed due to the rapid and comprehensive development and spread of the scientific and technological environment. information technologies that permeate all aspects of modern society. In this paper, the oxidation kinetics of carbon steel is investigated depending on the presence of copper (Cu). aimed at Determine the high

temperature oxidation behavior of Cu bearing steel. Hot shrinkage caused by Cu is the main problem treatment of tramp element containing steels. The experimental temperature range is determined depending on the steel deformation process. Oxidation experiments were carried out in an electric resistance furnace from 900 to 1200 °C with 100 °C intervals. High-temperature oxidation kinetics of Cu-containing carbon steel was investigated. Topographical Surface analysis of the samples was carried out using X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, and optical microscopy. Mass rate of return and kinetic results were evaluated algebraically. Segregation of Cu on steel surfaces at elevated temperatures and its anti-oxygen behavior was observed This is the case helps to know the characteristics of the processes and objects being studied mathematical modeling processes are widely used in computing. Methodical approach to model creation is based on classical principles and results are calculated based on these processes and is well described in the literature. The structure of the created model may differ in its content and description. The difference is determined by several levels of complexity from reproductive constructively and creatively. Different levels of complexity of the model depending on the level of preparation and the requirements for the model. At each level, specific mathematical models are created to solve specific problems. The geometric frame of the model covers this part a furnace filled with liquid metal. because of the symmetry of the furnace along the vertical plane, this perpendicular to the axis of the furnace, there is only half of the furnace should be taken into account in calculations. Geometry of the developed model of the anode furnace a reduction process consisting of the following items:

- # copper charge
- # natural gas inlet
- # outgassing - high copper surface.

Shrinkage is a periodic process that changes over time parameters, so it was done to calculate is a temporary system. Natural gas is supplied by movement and is in motion it is created by liquid copper in the form of bubbles. Reduce the process follows the reaction equation and occurs at and the boundary between gaseous and liquid phases remains relatively unchanged.

Today, this process has been completed the technology of the experimental industrial enterprise and its projection and investment operating costs are relatively low done in a conventional rotary processing furnace. Besides

characterized by increased kinetics. Improving and reducing the number of technologies emissions of combustion gases are also described. This was the purpose of the present work then modeling the reduction phase of this technology laboratory scale to obtain the design and we can see that it is structured based on operational optimal scale parameters. Picture 1, represents the chemical diagram of the contraction pilot industrial plant packed copper mold reactor.

Picture 1. Schematic drawing of the molded reduction system copper reactor of pilot industrial plant

It is known that copper refining at high temperature consists of the following operations: chemical reactions, melting of copper by molten heating, oxidation of impurities, alloying removal, deoxidation (recovery) of copper, copper spillage. The main ones that define the recycling process are: oxidation of compounds - based on differences in affinity for oxygen considered as copper and its compounds, which can be represented by alternative energy. the oxygen affinity of series elements, which are part of copper, decreases In the direction from Al to Au, the results of movement are equal. The oxidation stage begins with the process of blowing the copper solution with air. Due to the high concentration of copper in the solution, it is first oxidized, and then compounds are oxidized according to reactions:

For the maximum removal of unwanted reagents, the following are necessary: the greatest solubility of Cu_2O dissociation, the separation of the mixture with the minimum dissociation power. oxidation state. The elasticity of dissociation increases with increasing O_2 concentration in Cu_2O the copper solution separates. But significantly increasing the concentration of oxygen in copper

smelting is not recommended because copper does not dissolve excess Cu_2O and forms an independent solid or liquid phase on the solution surface.

Picture 2. State process representation diagram Cu–O (station Cu– Cu_2O)

Conclusions

In this article, we will look at how to create different mathematical models degrees in the example of high-temperature refining of copper. Mathematical models have been created that connect the oxygen concentration necessary for the oxidation of copper compounds with the main indicators of the metallurgical process: calculation of the mass of compounds containing various copper and solution temperature, the level of oxygen saturation of the bath. The models allow for operational calculation of the required amount of oxygen, therefore taking into account the oxidation of copper alloys with variable composition indicators of influence of selected parameters are taken into account. The results showed that copper dissociates at high temperatures and it acts as an oxygen barrier in the steel. surface. This mechanism leads to increased activation oxidation energy in low carbon steel. Both increase the transfer area between the coolant and the metal plates and the reduction in plate thickness was sufficient to improve the original design furnace port. This alternative design reduced the average metal surface temperature compared to the original design by 300 K, and the maximum temperature has decreased 750 K, thus preventing the risk of copper infiltration into steel plates. Finally, the low temperatures achieved in the upper port plates prevented anchoring assembly, reduces furnace maintenance costs. To conclude, the positive contribution of alternative designs to sustainability the processing is remarkable. This idea is mainly supported by potential eliminating hot gas leaks through the furnace port, which is the source of both uncontrolled pollutant emissions (mainly CO_2 and NO_x) and heat losses. Consequently, the proposed designs not only improve the mechanical integrity of the furnace, but also improve it the main energy consumption is reduced

-> The amount of copper found ineffective 900 °C for the oxidation rate of steel; however, at higher temperatures, copper increases mass growth steel grade. The copper content will be higher oxidation state of steel. Hematite occurs at 2% Cu containing steel scale, 0.2% Cu steel scale consists of magnetite and wustite.

-> formation of bubbles at the scale/metal interface restricts the diffusion of oxygen atoms into the interior parts of the material. under the presence of liquid copper scale also suppresses the oxygen diffusion pathway atoms. This mechanism acts as a protective surface position on the steel surface and consequently rises activation energy of oxidation in copper deposition steel. Copper bearing steel has an activation energy oxidation state is 159.10 kJ/mol, copper deposition is low steel has an activation energy of 150.90 kJ/mol.

-> Cu has higher oxidation resistance than iron, therefore remains in metallic form under the steel surface and causes separations on the steel surface. The separated copper moves to the austenite grain boundaries and reduces grain cohesion. Along with this mechanism as a result of the high temperature and rolling process macro cracks known as hot shortness are visible along the surface. O'telbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, gave several examples of the processes of their application in mining and presented to international journals the methods of automation of mining technologies through microprocessors and the technologies in mining at the same time. proved with several examples that it can be used in several technological processes. The use of modern technologies plays an important role in the development economy of the mine. It is necessary to pay attention to the parameters of technologies when automating processes in mining enterprises. Do not set the load beyond the limits of the technology, only then the technology will work for a long time without problems. In this article, I will inform you that if we install a microprocessor (automatic mode memory) in the technology in the mining enterprises, we will prevent the overloading of the technology. This ensures the operation of the enterprise and the safety of workers. Otelbayev Azizbek, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology, has articles on metallurgical processes, components of metals, and metal enrichment processes. Much research has been done on the metallurgical industry. A number of information on processes in metallurgical deposits, extraction of metals, corrosion of metals and extraction of metals by flotation methods are presented.

References:

1. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Yuldashev, S., Toshpulatov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). Geological-Geochemical and Mineralogical Properties of Basalt Rocks of Karakalpakstan.
2. Djaksimuratov Karamatdin Mustapaevich, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, & Mnajatdinov Dastan Mnajatdin o'g'li. (2021). PROPERTIES OF COAL, PROCESSES IN COAL MINING COMPANIES, METHODS OF COAL MINING IN THE WORLD. JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, 7(10), 231-236. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/32N4G>
3. Djaksimuratov, K., Toshev, O., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). MEASURING AND CRUSHING THE STRENGTH OF ROCKS USE OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SURFACTANTS FOR GRINDING.
4. Djaksimuratov, K., Ravshanov, Z., O'razmatov, J., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). Comprehensive monitoring of surface deformation in underground mining, prevention of mining damage. Modern technologies and their role in mining.
5. Djaksimuratov, K., O'razmatov, J., Maulenov, N., & O'telbayev, A. (2021). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING, ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION, PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION.
6. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). Improving the Efficiency of Excavators Increasing the Efficiency of Temporary Ditch Excavator.
7. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). MONITORING THE CONDITION OF THE DEPOSIT IN MINING ENTERPRISES. MODERN METHODS OF DETERMINING THE LOCATION OF MINERALS.
8. Djaksimuratov, K., Joldasbayeva, A., Bayramova, M., Tolibayev, E., & Maulenov, N. (2022). TECHNOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF UNDERGROUND EXCAVATION WORKS IN GEOTECHNICAL MONITORING SYSTEMS.
9. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Ametov, R., Rametullayeva, M., & Bayramova, M. (2022). MODERN TECHNICAL METHODS OF MONITORING LANDSLIDES IN OPEN MINES.
10. Joldasbayeva, A., Ametov, R., Embergenov, A., Maulenov, N., & Kulmuratova, A. (2022). Technology to prevent Methane or coal dust explosions in the mine.
11. Djaksimuratov, K., Maulenov, N., Rametullayeva, M., Kulmuratova, A., & Embergenov, A. (2022). Technology for Determining the Force of Impact on Buildings in the Vicinity during Blasting Operations in Mines.

12. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). CORROSION OF METALS AND FACTORS AFFECTING IT. METHODS OF PREVENTING CORROSION OF METALS.
13. Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi, Utepbaeva Gulnaz Saken qizi, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, Azizov Azatbek Jumabek o'g'li, & Yo'ldashova Hilola Baxtiyor qizi. (2022). AUTOMATION AND ROBOTIZATION OF UNDERGROUND MINES. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, 9(10), 20–28. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UYH93>
14. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, Zaytova Madina Nazarbay qizi, & Kulmuratova Aliya Janabay qizi. (2022). Conveyor belt structure and mode of operation in mines. Eurasian Journal of Engineering and Technology, 11, 72–80. Retrieved from <https://www.geniusjournals.org/index.php/ejet/article/view/2360>
15. Mustapaevich, D. K., Axmet o'g'li, M. N., Baxitbay qizi, J. A., Alisher o'g'li, O'telbayev A., & Ikromboy o'g'li, O. J. (2022). Model Of Stages of Determination of Strength of Dynamic Fracture of Rocks and Digital Technological Verification. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 230–239. Retrieved from <https://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/620>
16. Djaksimuratov Karamatdin Mustapaevich, Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, Ergasheva Zulxumor Abdaaliyevna, O'razmatov Jonibek Ikromboy o'g'li, & O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2022). Underground mine mining systems and technological parameters of mine development. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact Factor: 7.429, 11(10), 110–117. Retrieved from <https://www.gejournal.net/index.php/IJSSIR/article/view/1016>
17. Mustapaevich, D. K., Axmet o'g'li, M. N., Baxitbay qizi, J. A., Alisher o'g'li, O. A., & Ikromboy o'g'li, O. J. (2022). Methods of Determining the Effect of Temperature and Pressure on the Composition of Rocks. Vital Annex : International Journal of Novel Research in Advanced Sciences, 1(4), 98–106. Retrieved from <https://innosci.org/IJNRAS/article/view/393>
18. Ravshanov Zavqiddin Yahyo o'g'li, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li, Joldasbayeva Aysulu Baxitbay qizi, & Bayramova Minevvar Axmet qizi. (2023). MINING TECHNOLOGICAL EQUIPMENT THAT DETERMINES THE SLOPE ANGLES OF THE MINE BY MEANS OF LASER BEAMS. Neo Scientific Peer Reviewed Journal, 6, 17–23. Retrieved from <https://neojournals.com/index.php/nspj/article/view/96>

19. Yeshmuratova, A., Kulmuratova, A., Maulenov, N., & Otemisov, U. (2023). MINE BLASTING PROCESSES OPTIMIZATION STAGES OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY OF DETONATORS.
20. Ravshanov, Z., Joldasbayeva, A., Maulenov, N., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). Determination of mineral location coordinates in geotechnology and mining enterprises.
21. Djaksimuratov, K., Batirova, U., Otemisov, U., & Aytmuratov, S. (2023). STEPS FOR DETERMINING THE SLOPE ANGLE OF AN OPEN MINE.
22. Djaksimuratov, K., Batirova, U., Abdullaev, A., & Joldasbayeva, A. (2023). GATHERING COORDINATES OF THE GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL LOCATION OF THE MINE.
23. Ravshanov, Z., Joldasbayeva, A., Bayramova, M., & Madreymov, A. (2023). IN GEOLOGICAL AND GEOTECHNICAL PROCESSES IN THE MINE USE OF TECHNOLOGICAL SCANNING EQUIPMENT IN THE UNDERGROUND MINING METHOD.
24. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Maulenov, N., & Rametullayeva, M. (2022). Casting And Evaluation of Properties for an Aluminum Alloy Material and Optimizing the Quality Control Parameters.
25. Djaksimuratov, K., Jumabayeva, G., Batirova, U., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). GROUNDWATER CONTROL IN MINES
26. Abdiramanova, Z., Jumabayeva, G., Batirova, U., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). ACTIVITY OF TEBINBULAK IRON ORE MINING ENTERPRISES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN.
27. Qurbonov.A.A, Djaksimuratov Karamatdin Mustapaevich, & O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2021). FACTORS INFLUENCING THE CONDITIONS OF OPEN PIT MINING, ORE MASS AND DEFORMATION. PROCESSES THAT LEAD TO IMBALANCE DURING EXCAVATION. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 1(6), 45–49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5500210>
28. O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2022). STRENGTH PROPERTIES OF ROCKS AND FACTORS INFLUENCING THEM AND THE PROCESS OF CHANGING THE PROPERTIES OF ROCKS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6034442>
29. Joldasbayeva, A., Maulenov, N., Mnajatdinov, D., & O'telbayev, A. (2023). PROCESSES OF DRAWING UP A VENTILATION SYSTEM SCHEME IN MINES.
30. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). TECHNOLOGICAL MODES OF MONITORING THE LOCATION OF MINES IN THE MINE AND THE SLOPE BORDER OF THE BLAST AREA.

31. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., Amanbaev, N., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). PROCESSES OF BENEFICIATION AND EXTRACTION OF ORES IN IRON MINES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TEBIN BULAK IRON MINE).
32. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., Amanbaev, N., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). DETERMINATION OF VIBRATIONS CAUSED BY BLASTING PROCESSES IN OPEN PIT MINING AT MINING ENTERPRISES.
33. Maulenov, N., Joldasbayeva, A., O'razmatov, J., & Mnajatdinov, D. (2023). MOBILE TECHNOLOGICAL METHODS OF SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN SURFACE MINING.
34. Utepbaeva Gulnaz Saken qizi, Urazbayeva Aqmaral Sulayman qizi, Joldasbaeva Feruza Jan'abay qizi, O'telbayev Azizbek Alisher o'g'li. (2023). FOAM FLOTATION PROCESS, STAGES AND TECHNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7641035>
35. Patualieva, Q., Joldasbaeva, J., & Eshimbetova, M. (2023). STAGES OF USING GEODETIC METHODS IN OPEN MINING CONDITIONS.
36. O'TELBAYEVA Muhayyo Alisherovna. (2023). METHODOLOGY AND THEORY OF CHEMISTRY TEACHING IN SCHOOLS, METHODS AND PROCESSES OF THEIR STUDY. *Journal of Experimental Studies*, 2(2), 10–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7623700>
37. O'TELBAYEVA Muhayyo Alisherovna. (2023). ANALYSIS OF PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL METHODS AND APPROACHES. *Pedagogical and Psychological Studies*, 2(2), 12–16. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7624764>
38. Jumabayeva Guljahon Jaqsilikovna. (2023). CONTROL OF UNDERGROUND WATER IN THE MINE, DETECTION AND PREVENTION OF RISKS. *ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE*, 2(5), 159–166. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7648010>
39. Patualieva, Q. (2023). METHODS OF DETERMINING THE COORDINATE DIMENSIONS OF AN OBJECT ON MAPS, CARTOGRAPHY AND GEOGRAPHIC LOCATIONS.
40. Mustapaevich, D. K., o'g'li, M. N. A., qizi, J. A. B., o'g'li, O. A. A., & qizi, K. A. J. (2022). Calculation of the Technological Scheme of Traffic Control of Mine Transport in Open Mines. *International Journal on Orange Technologies*, 4(10), 34-42. Retrieved from <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJOT/article/view/3570>
41. Утемисов А. О., Юлдашова Х. Б. К. СИСТЕМЫ АВТОМАТИЧЕСКОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ //Universum: технические науки. – 2022. – №. 5-2 (98). – С. 45-47.

42. Utemisov, A. (2019). Таълим жараёнида компьютер ва инновацион технологияларнинг роли.
43. Ametov Bayram Tursynbaevich, Uzakbaeva Akmaral Sulayman Kizi, & Allamuratov Guljamal Bisengali Kizi. (2022). Wind Mill and Solar Energy. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 178–179. Retrieved from <https://zienjournals.com/index.php/tjet/article/view/3068>
44. Аметов, Б. Т. (2021). Возникновение И Распространение Ударной Волны В Твердом Теле. IJTIMOİY FANLARDA INNOVASIYA ONLAYN ILMİY JURNALI, 1(6), 42-44.
45. Аметов, Б. Т., Султанбаев, А. П., & Жангабаев, А. К. (2021). ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ И ПРОБЛЕМЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫХ ИСТОЧНИКОВ ЭНЕРГИИ. In КОНКУРС МОЛОДЫХ УЧЁНЫХ (pp. 72-74).
46. Tursynbaevich, A. B., Kizi, U. A. S., & Kizi, A. G. B. (2022). Wind Mill and Solar Energy. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 178-180.
47. АМЕТОВ Б. Т., АМИДУЛЛАЕВА Ю. Б. К., КИЗИ И. О. И. РАДИАЦИОННО-СТИМУЛИРОВАННОЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ ОПТИЧЕСКИХ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИК КВАНТОВО-РАЗМЕРНЫХ СТРУКТУР СОЕДИНЕНИЙ А2В6 // Studies in Economics and Education in the Modern World. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 9.
48. АМЕТОВ Б. Т., КИЗИ А. М. М., КИЗИ К. А. Ж. ВЛИЯНИЕ МИКРОВОЛНОВОЙ ОБРАБОТКИ НА СВОЙСТВА АРСЕНИДГАЛЛИЕВЫХ ДИОДНЫХ СТРУКТУР С БАРЬЕРОМ ШОТТКИ // ЛУЧШАЯ НАУЧНАЯ СТАТЬЯ 2022. – 2022. – С. 8-10.
49. Бубякин М. Ю. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ 3D ПРИНТЕРА ДЛЯ АДДИТИВНОГО ИЗГОТОВЛЕНИЯ ДЕТАЛЕЙ // КОНКУРС МОЛОДЫХ УЧЁНЫХ. – 2021. – С. 55-60.
50. Аметов Б. Т. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ СТРУКТУРЫ ТЕ-CDTE СО СВОЙСТВОМ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО ПЕРЕКЛЮЧЕНИЯ ПРИ ИМПУЛЬСНОМ ЛАЗЕРНОМ ОБЛУЧЕНИИ CDTE // Интернаука. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 186 часть 2. – С. 18.
51. A.A. Eshmuratova. (2022). MATCAD DASTURIDAN FOYDALANIB IKKI VA UCH O'LCHOVLI GRAFIKLARNI QURISH . Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(5), 534–539. Retrieved from <https://ojs.rmasav.com/index.php/ojs/article/view/341>
52. Kaipbergenov, Atabek Tulebergenovich, Askarbek Orazimbetovich Utemisov, and Hilola Bakhtiyor Kizi Yuldashova. "STEADY OF AUTOMATIC CONTROL SYSTEMS." Academic research in educational sciences 3.6 (2022): 918-921.
53. Tulebergenovich, Kaipbergenov Batirbek, and Utemisov Askarbek Orazimbetovich. "Classification and analysis of computer programs for the

physical preparation of athletes and expasure of prospects for their studies."
European science review 7-8 (2015): 11-13.

